

PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF PROSTATE CANCER

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According to the World Health Organization, in 2018, 1.3 million new cases of prostate cancer (PC) diagnosis and 359 thousand deaths due to this disease were registered, in connection with which PC was the second most common malignant neoplasm and the fifth leading cause of death in men worldwide [4; 8]. Improvement of diagnostic methods and the availability of an algorithm for screening patients increases the frequency of early diagnosis, thus, the percentage of cases with stage I-II of the disease from 2011 to 2021 increased from 47.7% to 60.7%. However, the detection rate of stage IV prostate cancer remains quite significant (22% of all cases of the disease), which causes a high mortality rate - within the first year from the moment of diagnosis, the mortality rate is 6.5%. In addition, a relapse often develops after radical surgical treatment [3].

In 70% of cases, prostate carcinoma is localized in its peripheral zone (usually in the posterior part of the gland, which allows palpating the tumor during a digital rectal examination). It is characteristic that on a section of the gland, the tumor tissue is granular and dense. If the tumor is located in the thickness of the prostate tissue, it is poorly visualized, but is easier to detect by palpation. With local spread, periprostatic tissue, seminal vesicles and the base of the bladder are usually affected, which in advanced forms of the disease can lead to urethral obstruction. Metastases initially spread through the lymphatic vessels to the level of the obturator lymph nodes and reach the para-aortic lymph nodes. Hematogenous dissemination occurs mainly to bone, especially the axial skeleton, but in some cases massive dissemination to viscera has been observed (rather the exception than the rule). Bone metastases are usually osteoblastic and, when found in men, strongly suggest prostate cancer. The lumbar spine is most commonly affected, followed in decreasing order of frequency by the proximal femur, pelvic bones, thoracic spine, and ribs.

Histologically, most prostate tumors are adenocarcinomas, which are characterized by the presence of well-defined, easily identifiable glandular structures [5]. The tumor glands are usually smaller in size and lined by a single layer of cuboidal cells or low columnar epithelial cells. The tumor glands are located closer to each other and characteristically lack ramifications or papillary

invaginations. The tumor glands lack the outer basal layer characteristic of glands of the normal organ. The cytoplasm of tumor cells varies from dull-light, characteristic of cells of unchanged glands, to distinctly amphophilic. The nuclei are large and often contain one or more large nucleoli. Some differences in the size of the nuclei and their shape are observed, but in general pleomorphism is not very pronounced. Mitotic figures are not characteristic. The problem of cancer diagnosis is not only in the insufficient amount of tissue obtained during needle biopsy for histological examination, but also in the fact that often biopsy samples contain only a few tumor glands among many normal ones.

Pathological diagnosis of prostate cancer is also difficult because the signs of malignancy can be subtle, which increases the likelihood of a false negative result. There are also many benign processes that mimic malignancy, which can also lead to misdiagnosis. Although there are several histological features specific for prostate cancer, such as perineural invasion, the diagnosis is made with a combination of tissue, cellular and some additional features. As noted earlier, the main distinguishing feature of a benign process in the prostate gland is the presence of basal layer cells, while their absence indicates prostate cancer [4]. Pathologists exploit this feature by using immunohistological markers to identify basal layer cells.

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